

Preparing datasets for sharing

Brian Mutinda

Mahidol Oxford Research Unit

&

Naomi Waithira

Mahidol Oxford Research Unit

University of Oxford

This course is developed as a collaborative effort and funded by the Wellcome Trust

Before pressing send, check...

- Data complete, appropriate
- Data formats
- Metadata including data dictionary/descriptors/coding scheme
- Licensing
- Dataset and Author Identifiers
- Volume and size limitations
- Language

Data complete, appropriate

- Versioning: Same dataset used for publication [record counts, file size, name, columns]
- Required variables are included in dataset*
- Dataset is de-identified or anonymized as necessary

Anonymization

ISO 29100:2011: “**process** by which all personally **identifiable** information (PII) is **irreversibly** altered in such a way that a PII principal can no longer be **identified** directly or indirectly, either by the PII **controller** alone or in collaboration with any other party.

Data de-identification

Removal or obscuring any direct and indirect personal identifiers from a dataset in a way that minimizes the risk of unintended disclosure of identity of individuals.

Image source: Our Daily Bread- Mood Mender

De-identification – Re-identification of persons possible eg by maintaining a list of identification numbers that link a de-identified dataset to original human subjects.

Anonymization - Re-identification of persons is not possible, because the links back to the subjects are irreversibly broken.

Health insurance Portability & Accountability Act

Expert determination

- Use of statistical & scientific principles to render information not individually identifiable
= Very small risk information can be used alone or in combination with other information to identify individual
- Must be done by a person with appropriate knowledge and experience
- Methods used and results of analysis to justify the determination must be recorded
- Certification of de-identification should be retained for at least 6 years from date of creation/date when last in effect

Example de-identification techniques

Generalization

- The value of a field is modified/replaced with a more general value
- For example, a date of birth can be generalized to a month and a year of birth

Suppression

- Specific values in the data set are removed from the data set (i.e. induced missingness)
- For example, a value in a record that makes it an outlier may be suppressed.

Randomization

- Adding noise to a field, data swapping and data generation
- The noise can be uniform or other type of distribution.
- For example, a date may be shifted a week forward or backward

Subsampling

- To disclose a random subset of the data rather than the full data set to the Quasi Identifier (QI)

Safe Harbor's 18 Identifiers

1. Names
2. Geographic subdivisions smaller than a State including zip codes, and their equivalent [geocodes](#)
3. All elements of dates (except year) or dates directly relating to an individual, including:
 - **birth date, admission date, discharge date, date of death;**
 - and all ages over 89 and all elements of dates (including year) indicative of such age, except that such ages and elements may be aggregated into a single category of age 90 or older;
4. Telephone numbers;
5. Fax numbers;
6. Electronic mail addresses;
7. Social security numbers;
8. [Medical record numbers;](#)
9. Health plan beneficiary numbers
1. Account numbers;
2. Certificate/license numbers;
3. Vehicle identifiers and serial numbers, including license plate numbers;
4. Device identifiers and serial numbers;
5. Web Universal Resource Locators (URLs);
6. Internet Protocol (IP) address numbers;
7. [Biometric identifiers](#), including finger and voice prints;
8. Full face photographic images and any comparable images; and
9. Any other unique identifying number, characteristic, or code.

safe harbor is an approved method of de-identification for any purpose by any covered entity, regardless of sophistication, it was **NOT** designed for research

Limited Data Set (LDS):

health information that excludes certain, listed direct identifiers

LDS: Retain Indirect Identifiers

- Five-digit zip code
- Dates of service (e.g., admission / discharge)
- Dates of birth and death
- Geographic subdivision (e.g., state, county, city, precinct), but not street address

LDS: Remove 16 Identifiers

- Name
- Postal address information (other than city, state, zip code)
- Telephone number
- Fax number
- E-mail address
- Social Security Number
- Medical record / prescription numbers
- Health plan beneficiary numbers
- Account numbers
- Certificate / license numbers
- Vehicle identity / serial numbers
- Device numbers
- Web URL
- IP address
- Biometric identifiers (e.g., fingerprints, retinal scans)
- Full face similar photographic images

[45 CFR §164.514(e)(2)]

Practical approaches

You must document measures taken to de-identify/anonymise data

Subject ID:

Replace the original subject id with a new random subject ID

Free text

- Remove all free text verbatim terms.

Birth date

- Replace birth date with age bands eg [0-1], [1-2][20-50]
- Do not report any specific age outliers, instead represent by a range, e.g “x to xx” or “xx or older” in the database.

Dates:

- Replace original dates related to individual subjects with new dates offset by a random number OR
- Replace all original dates by study days relative to a “baseline/reference date” that will be provided by study statisticians.
- This does not apply to birth date, date of death and other publicly available dates

Practical approaches

You must document measures taken to de-identify/anonymise data

Geographic Information

- Remove geographic information such as residence geocodes
- Report geographical information at high administrative levels eg country or region

Demographic Information

- Remove subject name initials
- Remove or aggregate ethnicity/race especially for minorities eg group all minorities under 'Other'
- Remove gender

Patient characteristics

- Consider parameters eg disabilities/peculiarities
- Consider presence of uncommon ailments/symptoms

Subject id	Site	Arm	Sex	Dob
TAP-001	LPR01	2	MALE	30-Nov-11
TAP-002	TYN01	1	FEMALE	30-Jul-13
TAP-003	TYN01	2	MALE	02-Jun-11
TAP-004	TYN01	1	MALE	03-Jan-13
TAP-005	TYN01	2	MALE	29-Dec-15
TAP-006	TYN01	1	FEMALE	03-Oct-14
TAP-007	TYN01	1	MALE	02-Aug-14
TAP-008	TYN01	2	MALE	23-Sep-10

Subject id	Site	Arm	Sex	Age (yrs)
203	A	2	MALE	>5
320	B	1	FEMALE	>5
289	B	2	MALE	>5
219	B	1	MALE	>5
146	B	2	MALE	1-5
257	B	1	FEMALE	1-5
174	B	1	MALE	1-5
214	B	2	MALE	>5

Subject id- modified to a randomly generated number

Site- recoded

Date of birth – replaced with age band

Check Your Understanding

You are conducting a survey to describe malaria prevalence among adult farmers and forest workers living or working in the Mekong region. The output of the survey is a heatmap of the Mekong region.

- a) What potential identifiers may be collected
 - a) Date of birth
 - b) Occupation
 - c) Residence
 - d) Place of work
 - e) Malaria status
- b) What de-identification strategies are practical?
- c) Any special considerations?

Exercise

A dataset provided in next slide and as handouts in course folder

- a) Can you spot potential person identifiers.
- b) How can this dataset be de-identified

subjID	Village	admdate	agey	agem	subjinit	sex	maltest	malspecies	occupation	travelday	travelwhy	pregnant	LMP
7	cardenas	27-Nov-15	28	0OG		Male	Slide	P. falci	forest worker		5 for wood cutting	N	
8	soroa	14-Dec-15	30	0FA		Male	RDT	P. falci	farmer: paddy /rice		5 for wood cutting	Y	22-May-15
9	garjania	01-Jan-16	32	0NH		Male	RDT	Mixed	farmer: paddy /rice		5 for wood cutting	N	
50	garjania	01-Jan-16	25	0GT		Male	RDT	P. falci	plantation worker		7	N	
51	garjania	20-Feb-16	2	0ST		Male	RDT	P. vivax	child		0	N	
52	bauta	16-Mar-16	25	0HT		Male	RDT	P. falci	plantation worker		7	N	
53	bauta	17-Mar-16	5	0PM		Male	RDT	P. falci	child		0	N	
54	bauta	22-Mar-16	7	0ST		Female	RDT	P. vivax	student		6	Y	11-Jan-16
55	bauta	08-Apr-16	37	0ST		Male	RDT	P. falci	plantation worker		7	N	
56	cardenas	24-Apr-16	27	0JT		Female	RDT	P. falci	housewife		7	Y	10-Dec-15
57	murapara	17-May-16	7	0ST		Female	RDT	P. falci	student		6	N	
58	cardenas	19-May-16	21	0BM		Female	RDT	P. vivax	forest worker		6	N	
59	cardenas	25-May-16	20	0JT		Male	RDT	Mixed	plantation worker		6 went to market	N	
60	soroa	26-May-16	12	0HT		Male	RDT	P. falci	child		0	N	
61	soroa	04-Jun-16	9	0CM		Female	RDT	P. falci	child		0	N	
62	garjania	05-Jun-16	22	0ST		Female	RDT	P. falci	housewife		6	N	
63	soroa	06-Jun-16	9	0LM		Male	RDT	P. falci	child		0	N	
64	garjania	06-Jun-16	9	0KM		Female	RDT	P. falci	child		0	N	
76	joarianala	27-Jul-15	23	0EM		Male	Slide	P. falci	student		5	Y	14-Feb-15

Before pressing send..

- Data complete, appropriate
- Data formats
- Metadata including data dictionary/descriptors/coding scheme
- License
- Dataset and Author Identifiers
- Volume and size limitations
- Language

Data formats

ST_ABB	YR	P_CAP	HWY	WATER	UTIL	PC	GSP	EMP	UNEMP	Capital
AL	1970	15032.67	7325.80	1655.68	6051.20	35793.80	28418	1010.5	4.7	30065.35
AL	1971	15501.94	7525.94	1721.02	6254.98	37299.91	29375	1021.9	5.2	31003.88
AL	1972	15972.41	7765.42	1764.75	6442.23	38670.30	31303	1072.3	4.7	31944.81
AL	1973	16406.26	7907.66	1742.41	6756.19	40084.01	33430	1135.5	3.9	32812.52
AL	1974	16762.67	8025.52	1734.85	7002.29	42057.1				
AL	1975	17316.26	8158.23	1752.27	7405.76	43971.1				
AL	1976	17732.86	8228.19	1799.74	7704.93	50221.1				
AL	1977	18111.93	8365.67	1845.11	7901.15	51084.1				
AL	1978	18479.74	8510.64	1960.51	8008.59	52604.1				
AL	1979	18881.49	8640.61	2081.91	8158.97	54525.1				
AL	1980	19012.34	8663.50	2138.52	8210.33	56589.1				
AL	1981	19118.52	8628.83	2218.91	8270.79	56481.1				
AL	1982	19118.25	8645.14	2215.84	8257.26	58021.1				
AL	1983	19122.00	8612.47	2230.91	8278.63	58893.1				
AL	1984	19257.47	8655.94	2235.16	8366.37	59446.1				
AL	1985	19433.36	8726.24	2253.03	8454.09	60688.1				
AL	1986	19723.37	8813.24	2308.99	8601.14	61628.1				
AZ	1970	10148.42	4556.81	1627.87	3963.75	23585.1				
AZ	1971	10560.54	4701.97	1627.34	4231.23	24924.1				
AZ	1972	10977.53	4847.84	1614.58	4515.11	26058.1				
AZ	1973	11598.26	4963.46	1647.88	4986.92	27304.1				

<https://3dinside.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/drone-mapping-software.jpg>

ln	no	patcod	iniid	tpt	datecol	crt	na	k	cl	ttprt	alb	glu	pk
1	1	15-1-001-MA	MA	ADM	05-Jun-15	43	47	21	38	70		5	7.8
2	2	15-1-003-MA	MA	ADM	07-Jun-15	21	27	7	25	3		2	8.2
3	3	15-1-004-NA	NA	ADM	08-Jun-15	115	110	91	113	174		3	14.5
4	4	15-1-005-SB	SB	ADM	12-Jun-15	114	195	68	202	67		5	18.4
5	5	15-1-006-HK	HK	ADM	14-Jun-15	50	32	117	40	343		194	13.6
6	6	15-1-006-HK	HK	24	15-Jun-15	177	17	41	22	193		177	15.6
7	7	15-1-007-HB	HB	ADM	14-Jun-15	93	51	50	32	255		6	17.1
8	8	15-1-007-HB	HB	24	15-Jun-15	42							
9	9	15-1-008-MB	MB	ADM	15-Jun-15	22	78	91	138	216		188	16.9
10	10	15-1-009-KA	KA	ADM	18-Jun-15	115	25	26	19	228		7	2.1
11	11	15-1-010-SA	SA	ADM	18-Jun-15	174	14	33	9	757		8	1.4
12	12	15-1-010-SA	SA	24	20-Jun-15	184							
13	13	15-1-010-SA	SA	48	20-Jun-15	159							
14	14	15-1-010-SA	SA	DC	25-Jun-15	162							
15	15	15-1-011-HU	HU	ADM	20-jun-155	57	69	12	55	70		2	18.1
16	16	15-1-011-HU	HU	24	21-Jun-15	64							
17	17	15-1-011-HU	HU	48	22-Jun-15	25							
18	18	15-1-011-HU	HU	DC	25-Jun-15	77							
19	19	15-1-012-MJ	MJ	ADM	23-Jun-15	67	54	30	50	301		3	18
20	20	15-1-012-MJ	MJ	6	23-Jun-15	65							
21	21	15-1-014-TT	TT	ADM	25-Jun-15	71	18	40	21	163		6	8.8

Include a data dictionary/
descriptor file/
code book to
describe data
fields

Metadata

- Meta = "an underlying definition or description". Metadata is data that describes other data.
- Metadata makes it easier to find datasets and to understand context and contents of the datasets.
- Examples: author, date created and date modified and file size

Metadata functions

- Findability

- Organizing links to resources based on audience or topic.
- Building these pages dynamically from metadata stored in databases.

- Facilitating interoperability

- Using defined metadata schemes, shared transfer protocols, and crosswalks between schemes, resources across the network can be searched more seamlessly.

Title

Dataset8909

Authors

Naomi Waithira ×

Search co-authors by name, full email or ORCID. Hit enter after each.

Categories

Select categories ▼

Item type

Select item type ▼

Keyword(s)

Add keywords for easy discovery. Hit enter after each

Description

Describe your data as well as you can. Formatting is preserved when pasting from other sources and counts towards character limits

Example- Figshare

Recording metadata

- Data management plan (DMP) : Include a brief statement on what metadata will be recorded, how it will be recorded and who will be responsible for recording and having oversight of metadata.

Examples:

Study metadata- registration record in ClinTrials.gov. Describes study objectives, sites, timelines, outputs

Database metadata- data dictionary, codebook

Dataset metadata-details recorded while uploading dataset on repository

Supporting documents

- Software needed to view or use data if applicable
- Source code to reproduce results
- Study protocol
- Case Record Form/ Questionnaire

Before pressing send..

- Data complete, appropriate
- Data formats
- Metadata including data dictionary/descriptors/coding scheme
- License
- Dataset and author Identifiers
- Volume and size limitations
- Language

Licensing

Data licences – repositories may have different terms of use and provide different licenses for the deposited material. Use license filters to determine appropriate license for your dataset/software. Some examples:

Data

- Public Domain Dedication (CC Zero)
- Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY)
- Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike (CC-BY-SA)
- Creative Commons Attribution-NoDerivs (CC-BY-ND)
- Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial (CC-BY-NC)
- Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike (CC-BY-NC-SA)
- Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs (CC-BY-NC-ND)

Software

- Artistic License 1.0, 2.0
- GNU General Public License 2 or later (GPL-2.0)
- Affero General Public License 3 (AGPL-3.0)
- Mozilla Public License 2.0
- GNU Library or "Lesser" General Public License 2.1 or later (LGPL-2.1), GNU Library or "Lesser" General Public License 3.0 (LGPL-3.0)
- Eclipse Public License 1.0 (EPL-1.0)
- Common Development and Distribution License (CDDL-1.0)
- The BSD 2-Clause "Simplified" or "FreeBSD" License , The BSD 3-Clause "New" or "Revised" License (BSD)
- The MIT License (MIT)
- Apache License 2

DATASET AND AUTHOR IDENTIFIERS

- **PID systems** – provide a stable identification within the repository (integrity) and allow long-term access

- e.g. PURLs, Handles, DOIs, and ARKs

- List of PIDs: <https://project-thor.readme.io/docs/project-glossary>

- **Author Identifier Systems (AID)** - allow each researcher to keep track of all their outputs

- e.g. ORCID ID, Scopus ID, ISNI, Google Scholar Profiles, ResearchGate profile etc

- list of various AIDs: <https://project-thor.readme.io/docs/author-identifier-catalogue>

Connecting Research
and Researchers

Before pressing send..

- Data complete, appropriate
- Data formats
- Metadata including data dictionary/descriptors/coding scheme
- License
- Dataset and author Identifiers
- Volume and size limitations
- Language

Volume, size, format limitations

- **Zenodo:** 50Gb per dataset, no file format restrictions
- **Figshare:** default 5Gb limit per file, no file format restrictions
- **Mendeley:** 2 GB, Unlimited storage if plan is purchased; has listing of preferred & acceptable file formats
- **Dryad Digital Repository:** 300Gb, no file format restrictions. Non-proprietary & openly documented formats preferred.

Language

- Can your dataset be understood by others?
- Translation maybe necessary

<https://www.honorsociety.org/sites/default/files/styles/large/public/dd.feature.language.jpg?itok=gO-WILJz>

THANK YOU